

Systematisation of Knowledge on Severe Accident Phenomena and Experiments for Preservation and Transmission

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ABSTRACT

As a contribution to the transmission of knowledge on severe accidents, a methodology for developing a Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT) for severe accident phenomena in light water nuclear reactors is proposed. The methodology takes into account the current state of knowledge as well as the importance for nuclear safety. The developed PIRT should identify the priorities for further research directions.

1 INTRODUCTION

The past decades have witnessed intense research in severe accidents in light water reactors concerning all accident phenomena (in-vessel phenomena, ex-vessel phenomena, containment phenomena, source term behaviour). In addition to already existing knowledge, this research has produced an additional vast amount of theoretical and experimental results. However, despite the capitalization of knowledge conducted through codes development and validation, further attention should still be given to preserve and pass on the expertise and capabilities for the research to be addressed in the coming decade to new generations in the severe accidents field. That is, a researcher new in any topic within severe accidents is faced (among others) with the following questions:

- what is the state-of-the-art in the knowledge about specific phenomena ?
- what further research would be the most necessary and useful ?

Namely, on one hand, the development of information and communication technologies in the past decades (that is, the amount of information that can be transmitted, and the speed with which it can be done), and of course the advent and the spreading of the Internet (that is, the accessibility of the information) have made the scientific and technical information accessible as never before, both in the sense of quantity (amount of papers, reports, books) and of possibility of access. Thus, on any given topic (in the present paper, limited to severe accidents), any newcomer may have at their disposal almost "instantly" much more material than they have the time to read and understand. However, without previous experience, selecting the material that is relevant to their problem might prove quite difficult. Sometimes, younger researchers or professionals can be helped by senior colleagues, from whom experience might be transmitted also in this way. However, leaving the problem of knowledge transmission to be solved in this way in general might be a much too unreliable way to deal with this issue, which is not only very important but also fundamental for the continuation of research in the nuclear field and the further development of use of nuclear energy. This shows the need to somehow synthesize the available documentation and the state of the research in a succinct way, so that such information is available for the forthcoming generation of nuclear researchers and other professionals. A synthesis of knowledge on severe accidents has already been well presented in a book, edited by Sehgal [1], but this textbook with emphasis on the fundamentals is not so useful for the purposes stated above. Reviews of research activities are also published from time to time [2-4] but, useful as they may be, do not offer a proper solution to the stated issues.

The European SEAKNOT project (2022-2026) was proposed to also fulfil the stated purposes (among other tasks). A Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT) on expected phenomena during a severe accident is being prepared. In addition to summarize the phenomena as done in various states of the art, the PIRT will also provide an assessment of the knowledge about the listed phenomena and of their safety significance. The methodology to prepare the PIRT is described and explained. However, as the work is currently in progress, no results are presented.

2 PHENOMENA IDENTIFICATION AND RANKING TABLE

2.1 General Considerations

The first publications about PIRTs appeared (to the best of the authors' knowledge) towards the end of the 20th century [5, 6]. Although we cannot exactly know the intentions of the authors, we may suppose that the basic idea was, after decades of research in the nuclear field on various topics, to "put some order" in the existing knowledge, both in the identification (that is, making a comprehensive list of phenomena that can supposedly take place) and in the importance (depending on the stated criterion).

PIRTs were initially proposed for phenomena involved in design-basis accidents in light water reactors. The purpose of the work discussed here is to devise a PIRT for severe accident phenomena, which is an order of magnitude more demanding. Namely, in design-basis accidents, most phenomena fall within so-called "thermal-hydraulics", that is fluid motion with heat and mass transfer. In severe accidents (in light water reactors), the scope of all phenomena that take place first in the reactor pressure vessel (RPV) prior to (eventual) vessel rupture and later outside the RPV after rupture is much wider (in terms of both involved materials and physical and chemical processes). However, that does not mean, that these earlier works should be disregarded. Rather, these valuable achievements should be taken as bases and further adapted to severe accident phenomena.

PIRT development is a collective process; that is, its value stems from being a summing-up of different contributions, which decreases the uncertainties of the evaluations and increases the reliability of the produced table. However, for this process to be consistent, each individual contribution should be produced using the "same way of thinking". Hence the necessity of, as much as possible, uniquely and precisely defining a methodology to be used by all contributors.

Nearly 20 years ago, a PIRT on severe accident phenomena was developed within the EURSAFE project [7]. More than one thousand identified phenomena were reduced to about one hundred on which further research was deemed necessary, as they were important for safety but still lacking sufficient knowledge. The number of identified phenomena was indeed high, but that depends very much on the range of considered time and length scales (discussed in the next section). The research performed during the period since that project necessitates an updated evaluation of the research needs.

So far, some PIRTs were proposed in the field of severe accidents, but they were either limited to specific systems or phases of severe accidents [8, 9], or were not based on a comprehensive analysis [10].

2.2 Time and Length Scales

Before identifying the phenomena, consistency requires that the time and length scales on which phenomena are considered are defined. Unfortunately, perfect consistency can never be achieved. As a compromise between rigid formal definitions and no definition at all, one should accept approximate loose descriptions, described by illustrative examples and considered case-by-case for different systems.

The time scale, considered in the present work, is from a fraction of an hour up to a few hours (even if some processes take much longer, but that is not the time scale of the phenomena occurring). For instance, the ablation of the RPV wall may be considered, but not the RPV rupture itself, as this is an event that occurs almost instantaneously (that is, one moment, there is no flow of the core melt, and the next moment, the core melt flows out of the vessel). And anyway, it is vessel wall ablation that should be researched, as this is the phenomenon that leads to conditions at which vessel rupture is bound to occur. A similar dilemma occurred with combustion in the containment as, relatively to the entire accident scenario, it is just a brief process leading from one state to another; however, it was decided to keep combustion as a phenomenon.

The length scale, considered in the present work, is from a fraction of a system up to an entire system. For instance, combustion in the containment is considered as such, but not the interaction of turbulent eddies with the flame front that leads to wrinkling and causes flame acceleration due to increase of the surface on which the combustion chemical reaction takes place which increases the combustion rate. Another example might be that melt fragmentation into droplets when spilling into a coolant pool is considered, but not the detailed hydrodynamics that lead to fragmentation (again, on the level of turbulent eddies). As a final example, the melting of the reactor core metals is considered as a whole, not the individual melting of the cladding and the fuel rod spacers, say.

2.3 First Subdivision of Phenomena

A "classical" first subdivision of severe accident phenomena that somehow came about (for whatever reasons) is the following: in-vessel phenomena (essentially core degradation and melting, followed by core melt behaviour in the RPV lower plenum), ex-vessel phenomena (essentially fuel-coolant interaction that might eventually lead to steam explosions, and molten-

core-concrete interaction), containment phenomena (essentially atmosphere stratification and mixing that might cause high concentrations of combustible gases in some regions, and combustion that is a possible consequence of that) and source-term phenomena (essentially aerosol behaviour and physico-chemical processes involving fission products). This initial subdivision is mostly based on the system/location where phenomena occur. However, as many phenomena occurring in these different groups are intertwined, it was decided to use a first subdivision based on the phases of the severe accident, so that the phenomena will be divided into those occurring during the "in-vessel phase" and those occurring during the "ex-vessel phase" (with some phenomena of course occurring during both phases). Although this sounds similar to the earlier subdivision, it is fundamentally different, because it is not a "location-based" subdivision but a "time-based" one.

2.4 Ranking of Phenomena

As any ranking of anything in the universe (be it matter or process), the ranking, that is the ordering based on (some) *grading*, depends on the established criteria. Within the SEAKNOT project, the main purpose is to identify those severe accident phenomena which need further research most, either because they dominate the remaining uncertainties or because they play an important role during the mitigation of a severe accident.

The grading process prior to ranking will consider the following two main elements:

1. Knowledge: how thoroughly the phenomenon under evaluation is (supposed to be) known.
2. Safety significance: how important the phenomenon is deemed to be for nuclear safety (that is, safety of nuclear power plants).

2.4.1 Characterisation of knowledge

"Knowledge" is a broad term that may be understood in a different way by different people; this is especially true in the field of severe accidents where, for instance, many things can be known empirically from experience without proper theoretical explanation or, inversely, some very sophisticated models might have been proposed but were never validated experimentally. In order to (at least somewhat) avoid confusion and (as much as possible) systematize the knowledge characterization, the knowledge assessment is split into "Data" and "Model":

- "Data" refers to how well a phenomenon is known from experimental observations (be they qualitative or quantitative).
- "Model" refers to the physical and/or chemical understanding of a phenomenon (that is, to the fundamental causes and effects, not to the validity of specific existing models).

A three-level grading is defined for both Data and Model: Low, Medium, and High. The meanings of each of the three levels are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Three-level grading for Data and Model

	Low	Medium	High
Data	No data available	Data available, but not directly applicable	Data available & qualified for validation
Model	No model available	Model available but highly uncertain	Model validated & implemented in codes

2.4.2 Grading of knowledge

Different combinations of Data and Model gradings should result in the grading of knowledge. This is shown in Table 2, with some rationales provided here. First, no matter how sophisticated models of some phenomena might be, if no data are available to compare the model results with, Knowledge should be considered as Low. Namely, it is often assumed that if some model is based on established fundamental laws of nature, it must be "right" (in the usual sense of the term) and thus the phenomenon itself is understood because it is described in mathematical terms. Perhaps that may be true in some fields, but in severe accidents, no model has been developed so far based solely on fundamental laws, but some empiricism (whether based on physical intuition or not) always had to be included. Thus, models might always be "wrong" (again, in the usual sense of the term) and, if their results are not compared with experimental data, they cannot be considered as "knowledge".

Second, to go to the extreme case, a necessary condition for Knowledge to be considered as "High" is that (at least) a model that is extensively and comprehensively validated against experimental data exists. That is, the existence of such a model shows that the cause and effect mechanisms of the phenomenon are understood (although this is not a formal proof).

If we continue with Model, but on the other end (that is, Low), we see that the same logic as to Data Low applies to Model Low (that is, Model Low means Knowledge Low) for Data Low and Data Medium, but not for Data High: for this combination, Knowledge is considered Medium. The rationale for this asymmetric treatment (which is preferential for Data) is that Data High at least tells us some (supposedly true) things about the phenomenon, as they were observed experimentally, whereas Model High without validation does not necessarily tell us anything true about the phenomenon.

The rest of the cases are considered Medium: these are just the remaining combinations, considered as such because of lack of Data High or Model High or both.

Table 2. Composition of the three-level grading for Knowledge (L: Low; M: Medium; H: High)

		Data		
		Low	Medium	High
Model	Low	L (Unknown)	L (Qualitative understanding)	M (Bases for "known" set)
	Medium	L (Uncertain approximation)	M (Qualitatively assessed approximation)	M (Soundly assessed approximation)
	High	L (Uncertain model)	M (Qualitatively assessed model)	H (“Known”)

2.4.3 Grading of research priorities

Finally, to produce the PIRT (according to the purposes stated earlier), the safety significance should be included. Table 3 shows how knowledge and safety significance are combined to define priorities for further research. Contrary to Table 2, there is (almost) no preferential treatment (maybe some little for the safety significance, as M1 denotes a higher priority than M2).

First, Safety significance Low dominates all the rows: in that case, the priority is always Low, whatever the Knowledge. Second, Knowledge High dominates all the columns: in that case, the priority is always Low, whatever the Safety significance (of course, it is assumed here, that Knowledge High is "high enough").

The only extreme case of Priority High is a combination of Safety significance High and Knowledge Low: phenomena characterised as such are those for which further research is the most needed.

The other cases are remaining combinations and ranked as Medium. However, a slight distinction is made between Safety significance High and Knowledge Medium (M1: Medium High), Safety significance Medium and Knowledge Low (M2: Medium) and both Safety significance and Knowledge Medium (M3: Medium Low). As already stated, this grading gives to safety significance a slightly more importance than to knowledge.

Table 3. PIRT grading according to research priorities (L: Low; M1: Medium high; M2: Medium; M3: Medium low; H: High)

		Safety significance		
		Low	Medium	High
Knowledge	Low	L (Poor understanding; irrelevant)	M2 (Poor understanding; mild effect)	H (Poor understanding; impacting)
	Medium	L (Some understanding; irrelevant)	M3 (Some understanding; mild effect)	M1 (Some understanding; impacting)
	High	L (Sound understanding; irrelevant)	L (Sound understanding; mild effect)	L (Sound understanding; impacting)

In the end, each phenomenon that is considered (in both "in vessel" and "ex-vessel" phases of the severe accident) should be assigned one of the priorities from Table 3. This will in turn lead to their ranking.

CONCLUSIONS

- A concise synthesis of the vast amount of accumulated knowledge on severe accidents in light water reactors should be produced and made widely available so that the "knowledge about this knowledge" is passed to new generations of potential nuclear experts.
- A suitable way of synthesizing the knowledge is to produce a Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT) that takes into account all possible severe accident phenomena known so far.
- As PIRT development is not uniquely defined, a methodology for grading phenomena which will result in their ranking according to the stated criteria of needed further research is proposed.

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